

SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING IN THE MODERN CENTURY

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Annotation. This article provides information about the process of simultaneous interpretation in the 21st century. Despite the fact that simultaneous translation is one of the youngest types of translation, it is widely used worldwide. In order for simultaneous translation to be successful, it is necessary to study the material in sufficient detail in advance and all available information that can be used in the speaker's speech; improvisation in the process of simultaneous translation should be minimal, taking into account the fact that during simultaneous translation the interpreter has practically no time to thinking about what was said, and there is no opportunity to clarify or repeat the information heard. This is the main difference between simultaneous and consecutive translation.

Key words: information, translation, communication, journalists, correspondents, commentators, television cameramen, international meetings, conferences, symposiums.

The 21st century poses new challenges in the information space of humanity. Thanks to mass information, the role of translation in the life of mankind is steadily increasing. Today, translation connections cover almost all spheres of human activity. The movement of information flows knows no boundaries, no time, no space. The endless diversity of the modern world is conveyed through the media in the feelings and interpretations of numerous participants in the international information process - journalists, correspondents, commentators, television cameramen. Therefore, the importance of translation activities is constantly growing. Oral, and especially simultaneous translation, is without a shadow of a doubt the most complex type of all existing types of translation. Both consecutive and simultaneous interpreting require serious professional skills, long-term work experience and deep knowledge of the language from the translator.

Naturally, the process of simultaneous translation involves a number of difficulties.

Firstly, the work of an interpreter in conditions of simultaneous listening and speaking requires constant concentration and continuous speaking. A situation of dual attention arises, caused by the need to constantly compare two languages and switch from one code to another. This leads to the fact that after 20-30 minutes. When interpreting, the interpreter becomes fatigued in the articular apparatus, self-control decreases, and serious and sometimes ridiculous errors appear in the translation text, even in their native language [2].

The second difficulty of simultaneous translation is related to the translator's reaction speed, or rather, his reactivity. The synchronized player is forced to instantly react every second to words and word combinations perceived by ear. Therefore, a slow person, even with an excellent command of a foreign language, is unlikely to become a good synchronized swimmer.

To work as a simultaneous interpreter, it is not necessary to have an impeccable command of the usual set of conversational standards of a foreign language. Namely, this aspect of a foreigner's speech, together with pronunciation, reveals his "foreignness" when communicating with native speakers. And if pronunciation, if desired, can be practiced in the most boring phonetic exercises, then remember and correctly use the gender of nouns, conjugation of irregular verbs, and most importantly - endless exceptions to the rules, for a

person even with outstanding memory in conditions of isolation from the corresponding language environment is a task of extreme difficulty.

Initial requirements for a simultaneous interpreter [4]:

- fluent language skills;
- grammatically correct speech;
- wide vocabulary;
- knowledge of a large number of cliches and the ability to instantly associate the translated text with them;
- lightning-fast reaction;
- concentration;
- endurance.

What led to the fact that simultaneous interpretation replaced consecutive interpretation at many official international events? The answer lies in the fact that after the Second World War, at various kinds of international meetings. Conferences, symposiums, the number of working languages has increased sharply. Participants in such events now included China, and Latin American countries [3]. And if until the end of the Second World War the working languages of international organizations were only French and English, then after its end and the victory over fascism, Russian, Chinese and Spanish were also added to these two languages. In this situation, consecutive translation would have taken several times longer (after all, there were now 5 working languages, not 2), and people's eyes turned to simultaneous translation [5]. However, we should not forget that the quality of the translation has suffered to some extent, since consecutive translation, when properly performed, gives better results than simultaneous translation.

The 21st century poses new challenges in the information space of humanity. Thanks to mass information, the role of translation in the life of mankind is steadily increasing. Today, translation connections cover almost all spheres of human activity. The movement of information flows knows no boundaries, no time, no space. The endless diversity of the modern world is conveyed through the media in the feelings and interpretations of numerous participants in the international information process - journalists, correspondents, commentators, television cameramen. Therefore, the importance of translation activities is constantly growing.

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